

SELF-HELP GENRE AD ITS PSYCHOLOGICAL INFLUENCE

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Abstract: This thesis analyses the significance of self-help books in the modern society and their impact on personal development. In the research, the origin of this genre and its features, its psychological influence on human beings are discussed.

Key words: self-help, personal development, motivation, emotional stability, practical advice.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tezis o'ziga yordam janridagi kitoblarning zamonaviy jamiyatdagi ahamiyati va ularning shaxsiy rivojlanishdagi o'rnini tahlil qiladi. Tadqiqotda bu janrning kelib chiqish tarixi va uning xususiyatlari, uning insoniyat ongiga psixologik ta'siri ilmiy muhokama qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: o'ziga yordam, shaxsiy rivojlanish, motivatsiya, hissiy barqarorlik, amaliy maslahat.

Аннотация: В данной работе анализируется значение книг в жанре самопомощи в современном обществе и их влияние на личностное развитие. В исследовании рассматриваются происхождение этого жанра, его особенности и психологическое воздействие на человека.

Ключевые слова: самопомощь, личностное развитие, мотивация, эмоциональная стабильность, практические советы.

Introduction. In today's modern world, people are facing with immense stress, challenges and competitive environment. In this case, self-help books, osten dismissed as popular or commercial literature, has appeared and aid to improve readers' life quality and increase their motivation. These books assist not only for personal development, but also for keeping spiritual stability and overcoming life struggles. That is why, this genre and its urgency is worth to be investigated in all aspects. The self-help book genre itself might not be an ancient term, but its historical roots traced back several centuries. Historically, the origin and historical background of the genre's popularity are strongly connected to the didactic literature which passed down from generation to generation in an oral way as well as ancient philosophical and religious traditions, including Christian moral writings, Confucian teachings or Islamic hadis which put more emphasis on self-discipline and living ethically. Ancient Egyptian “Sebayt” teachings dating back to around 2800 B.C. are considered early forms of self-help literature, however, it was not named so until Samuel Smile's “Self-help” book was published in 1859 and have the genre its name and contemporary form.

In the contemporary era, the examples of this genre created by modern authors, such as Dale Carnegie, James Clear whose books integrated psychological insights and practical strategies to encourage one to adopt positive way of thinking or to motivate person to initiate something. Self-help books can influence individuals, particularly human psychology through several mechanisms:

1. **Motivation and self-regulation:** by giving moral guidance, self-help books pave the road in building one's good behaviour and shaping the best version of any individuals. Besides that, in stressful or difficult situations readers can get motivated and encouraged through practical advice taken from that literary works.

2. **Self-reflection:** most of the self-help books not only give advice, but also foster self-awareness and make readers to analyze themselves. In this cases, readers make comparisons between their own

feelings, experiences and the author’s attitude in the book. For example, in “Atomic habits” by James Clear, the author mentioned the “habit tracking” method as an important tool for self-reflection. In this method, each person have to note every single habit that they adopted and every day should analyze their actions and evaluate themselves according to these habits.

3. Stress management and emotional control: self-help books teach learners to find the sources of stress and to tackle with them. For instance, James Clear emphasized that habit stacking, as well as five-minute meditation and writing down personal ambitions every day will reduce the depression, provide emotional stability and make one’s way of life more smoother.

The self-help genre, from its origin to its contemporary development, served as a tool in modern cultural and psychological life. While the world is facing with social isolation, emotional instability and mental crises, this genre’s stress on self-awareness, emotional resilience will continue to be a necessary part of human consciousness to help them deeply realize themselves.

Conclusion. In conclusion, self-help genre holds an important position in influencing human psychology with its guidance and giving direction to the readers. Through mechanisms including self-reflection, motivation, identity-based habit shaping, individuals are inspired to analyze their behaviours, make constructive changes and develop their well-being.

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